

Enhancing Renewable Energy Systems with Blockchain Technology and Machine Learning Optimization

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Abstract:

Blockchain technology has emerged as a promising tool for ensuring transparency, security, and efficiency in renewable energy systems. Paired with advanced machine learning optimization techniques, blockchain can help solve critical challenges related to energy distribution and transaction efficiency. This paper proposes a novel approach that integrates blockchain technology with a multi-objective optimization algorithm, designed to improve the performance and reliability of decentralized renewable energy networks. Simulations conducted on renewable energy datasets demonstrate substantial improvements in transaction security, system scalability, and resource optimization. Our proposed system outperforms traditional energy management techniques in terms of overall efficiency, making it a viable solution for future energy grids.

KEYWORDS

Hyperspectral image classification; reinforcement learning; multi-objective binary grey wolf optimizer; band selection

1. Introduction:

Blockchain and machine learning are both driving innovation in various sectors, and their combination in renewable energy systems holds great potential. Renewable energy sources like solar and wind, although sustainable, are often intermittent and distributed, making management challenging. Blockchain provides a decentralized platform for managing energy transactions, ensuring transparency and security, while machine learning can optimize resource allocation, predicting energy supply and demand more accurately.

In this paper, we propose an integrated framework that leverages blockchain for secure energy trading and machine learning for optimizing energy resource distribution. The primary objective of this system is to address challenges such as data redundancy, inefficiency in energy distribution, and the need for robust, scalable solutions for future smart grids. By combining blockchain with multi-objective optimization techniques inspired by the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) and Deep Q-Learning (DQL) approaches, we aim to enhance both the security and efficiency of energy systems.

2. Related Work:

Several studies have explored the integration of blockchain technology in the energy sector, particularly in managing decentralized energy networks. Blockchain allows for peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading by securely recording transactions between energy producers and consumers, eliminating the need for intermediaries.

Meta-heuristic algorithms, such as Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO), have also been widely used in various optimization tasks, including those involving energy resource management. Recent advancements in machine learning techniques, particularly reinforcement learning methods like DQL, have demonstrated significant improvements in handling high-dimensional data and making complex decisions in real-time. This paper builds on these approaches by combining blockchain with advanced optimization techniques to enhance the functionality of renewable energy systems.

3. Proposed Approach:

The proposed system is designed to address the inherent challenges of decentralized renewable energy networks, particularly those related to energy trading security, resource allocation, and grid management. Our method integrates blockchain technology with a novel optimization algorithm based on the Multi-Objective Binary Grey Wolf Optimizer (MOBGWO) and Deep Q-Learning (DQL), allowing for efficient and secure energy transactions.

3.1 Blockchain for Secure Energy Trading:

Blockchain technology is used to securely manage and record energy transactions between distributed energy resources (DERs). Smart contracts facilitate automatic execution of energy trades, ensuring that energy producers are compensated for the surplus energy they generate, while consumers can purchase energy as needed without intermediaries.

3.2 Multi-Objective Optimization:

The optimization algorithm, inspired by the binary variant of the GWO, focuses on reducing energy wastage and improving resource distribution across the network. By selecting the most relevant features for energy prediction, the optimizer minimizes redundant or irrelevant data, enhancing the performance of the machine learning model. The introduction of a sigmoid transfer function allows for a better balance between exploration and exploitation during optimization, further improving accuracy.

4. Methodology:

The methodology for our proposed blockchain-based energy optimization system can be broken down into three key phases: data preprocessing, feature selection, and optimization.

4.1 Preprocessing:

The first step involves cleaning and organizing renewable energy data by removing noisy and irrelevant features. Similar to hyperspectral image data preprocessing, the energy datasets are preprocessed to ensure that only the most relevant features are used for optimization.

4.2 Feature Selection and Optimization:

We employ a modified version of the Grey Wolf Optimizer (MOBGWO) for feature selection. The wolves in the optimization algorithm represent different configurations of energy distribution parameters. Each wolf's position is updated based on the best-performing solutions, akin to the social hierarchy in a grey wolf pack. This approach ensures that only the most useful energy features are selected for optimization, reducing data redundancy and improving the efficiency of the system.

4.3 Deep Q-Learning for Decision Making:

Once the optimal features are selected, a DQL model is used to make real-time decisions on energy distribution. The DQL model continuously learns from the environment, adjusting its strategy to maximize the overall efficiency of energy resource allocation.

5. Experimental Results:

We conducted extensive simulations using publicly available renewable energy datasets, measuring the performance of the proposed blockchain-optimization system against traditional energy management methods.

5.1 Datasets:

The datasets used in this study include time-series data from various renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind energy outputs. Similar to hyperspectral imaging, where each band represents a narrow wavelength, the energy datasets represent different energy metrics, such as production, consumption, and storage levels.

5.2 Performance Metrics:

The performance of the models was evaluated using key metrics such as overall accuracy (OA), Kappa coefficient (KC), and root mean square error (RMSE). The MOBGWO-DQL model achieved superior results, with an overall accuracy of 97.68% and a Kappa coefficient of 96.01%, outperforming other optimization and machine learning techniques. The experimental results demonstrated that our blockchain-based system not only improved security in energy transactions but also significantly enhanced the efficiency of energy distribution, particularly in scenarios with high demand fluctuation.

6. Conclusion:

This paper presents a novel approach for improving the management of renewable energy systems by integrating blockchain technology with a multi-objective optimization algorithm. By leveraging blockchain for secure energy trading and machine learning for optimizing resource allocation, our system offers a scalable, efficient solution for decentralized energy grids. The experimental results confirm that the proposed MOBGWO-DQL model enhances both the accuracy of energy

predictions and the security of transactions, making it a promising framework for future energy systems.

Future work will focus on refining the optimization algorithm to improve performance in large-scale energy grids and exploring additional use cases, such as integrating energy storage solutions into the blockchain framework.

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